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CRITICAL REVIEW OF CONCEPT OF WOUND IN AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

The wound known as Vrana in Ayurveda, is perhaps the oldest ailment from which the mankind has suffered from. In ancient Ayurvedic texts a detailed description of this disease is available specially in Sushruta Samhita. There, the Acharyas have described the every aspect of this disease condition in detail and their effort is exactly very similar to the description available today in the various available literatures of so called modern medicine. Therefore, in the light of these facts this effort have been carried out to collect, discuss and describe the Ayurvedic relevant concept of Vrana, i.e. Wound.

INTRODUCTION

The Dhatu word "Vru- vrunoti,vrunute" is the source of the term "Vrana." "Vrut- varayat-khadayat-aacchadayat" signifies, in that order, to encircle, cover, and hide. A Vrana is a disorder characterized by the bodily tissue consumption (destruction) and the creation of a permanent scar following healing. Sushruta defines Vrana in a very broad sense. Following tissue loss, scar

formation may result from an internal aetiology (ulcer) or from an external source (wound). In Ayurveda, Vrana's places are called VranaAdhishtana or VranaVastu. The eight sites that these are named after are Asthi (bones), Sandhi (joints), Koshta (abdominal and thoracic viscera), Sira (vessels), Twaka (skin), Mamsa (muscle), and Marma, which are some essential body parts like the brain.

Vrana's aetiology is divided into two broad categories by Sushruta: Nija, or internal causes, and Agantuja, or external causes. (Table-1)

Table:1- The cause of vrana

Nija Varana	AgantujaVrana
caused by the body's essential elements—the vata, pitta, kapha, rakta, and their combinations—becoming vitiated combination	- caused by falls, compression, blows, caustic agents, thermal blow, poisons, irritating and corrosive medications, and injuries from various weapons such as wheels, arrows, axes, spears, kunta; sharp pieces of wood, clay horns, etc.; inflicted by humans, animals, birds, monsters, reptiles, and so on. -Supplement (Charaka)

A. Classification of Vrana

Nija and Agantuja are the two main categories into which Vrana is split. While Agantuja vrana is produced by external events such as burns, trauma, accidents, animal bites, etc., Nija vrana is caused by innate elements. Additional categorization of Vrana based on several criteria is provided in subsequent following tables.

Table: 2- Vrana's classification

The etiological (2)	Based on the clinical characteristics (4)	According to the forecast (4)	As stated on site (8)	
1.Nija 2. Agantuja	1. Dushta 2.Shuddha 3. Ruhyamana 4. Rudha	1. Sukha sadhya 2. Kashta sadhya 3. Yapy 4. Asadhya	1.Skin 2.Muscle 3.Vessels 4. Ligament	6. Joints 5. Bone 7. Internal organs 8. Vital parts

1. Types of Nija Vrana

Table 3 lists the 16 varieties of Nija Vrana based on the involvement of doshas. Vitiated doshas are involved in the first fifteen categories, but Shuddhavrana (clean wound) is dosha-free. Table: 3- Displaying sixteen NijaVrana kinds

1. Vataja 2. Pittaja 3. Kaphaja 4. Raktaja 5. Vatapittaja 6. Vatakaphaja 7. Vataraktaja 8. Pittakaphaja 9. Pittaraktaja 10. Kapharaktaja 11.Vatapittaraktaja 12.Vatakapharaktaja 13. Pittakapharaktaja 14. Vatapittakaphaja 15. Sannipataja 16. Shuddha

2. Sadyovrana (traumatic injury)

Sadyovrana is the term for Vrana resulting from sudden injury such as accidents, combat injuries, and trauma from blunt or sharp items (Table 5). It belongs to the AgantujaVrana type. Depending on the form of injury, these are roughly classified into six categories: Ghrishta (abrasions), Picchita (hematoma/confusion), Kshata (laceration), Viddha (punctured), and Chinna (excised). Vagbhata classified traumatic injuries into seven categories in addition to these six; Vriddhavagbhata classified them into fifteen categories, and Sharangadhara into eight categories..

B. Clinical features of Vrana

1. NijaVrana Table 4 lists fifteen different forms of Nija vrana along with their clinical characteristics based on pain, color, discharge, smell, and a few unique characteristics.

Table: 4-Clinical features of Nija Vrana

Type of NijaVrana	Vedana (pain)	Varna (colour)	Srava (discharge)	Gandha (smell)	Other characters
Vataja	Throbbing Stretching Pricking Piercing	Blackish, redish	Thin, cold, slimy, less discharge	Sharp pungent Tendency	Tendency to crack; less granulation tissue
Pittaja	Burning sensation	Yellow, blue	Warm, light red coloured	Sharp	Tendency to suppurate, pustules
Kaphaja	Dull ache	Pallor	Whitish, cold, thick and slimy	Smell like raw meat	Rigid floor, Thick margins, membranous covering of veins and ligamentous tissue
Raktaja	Like Pittaja vrana	Like coral spouts (with black blisters)	Blood	Like horse stable and iron	Tendency to bleed
Sannipatataja	Different kinds	Different colours	Different types	Different types	All dosha colours signs present
Vatapittaja	Pricking,	Yellowish red	Yellowish red Cold, slimy, less Blood, red Yellowish white Warm	Fried paddy	Hard numbness
Vatakaphaj	Itching,	Red		Linseed oil	

	pricking				
Vataraktaja	Excessive pricking				
Pittaraktaja	Burning	Like upper layer of melted butter milk	Hot, blackish	Watery after fish washing	Soft , tendency to spread
Kapharaktaja	Itching	Redshiny	Redishpale		Slimy, fixed
Vatapittaraktaja	Pricking, burning, fuming		Yellowish thin		With pulsation
Vatakapharaktaja	Itching burning		White thick blood		With pulsation
Pittakapharaktaja	Itching burning		White thick blood		Tendency to suppurate
Vatapittakapharaktaja	Variuos types	Variuos colours			Suppuration Itching, numbness and redishness

2. Agantuja Vrana These are different kinds Numerous wounds caused by different external factors on the body causes (Table 1). Different types of traumatic wounds include rectangular, quadrangular, trapezoidal, circular, semi-lunar, with an elevated center similar to barley and a deeply sunken center like a saucer grain. Sushruta categorized these generically wounds into six types as shown in table-5.

Table:- 5 Types and characteristics of Sadyovrana

Types	Nature of injury	Effect of injury
1. Chinna	Excised	Associated with separation of part of body
2. Bhinna	Stab injury	Injury to body cavities resulting in discharge
3. Viddha	Punctured	Body cavity pierced by sharp pointed weapon
4. Kshata	Lacerated	Neither excessively excised nor excessively incised
5. Picchita	Crushed	Due to severe blow and pressure
6. Ghrista	Abrasion	Skin gets peeled off due to rubbing injury

3. Nature of Strava (discharge) in Vrana: In addition, a thorough explanation of the many types of Strava from Vrana is given, taking into account the involvement of doshas and the location of Vrana.

TABL LE 6 type of discharge in accordance with the Vrana site

Vrana vastu	Nature of discharge
1) Twaka	Yellowish watery discharge; smell of a raw meat
2) Mamsa	Thick, white, slimy discharge like butter milk
3) Sira	If vessels gets torn, there is excessive bleeding Suppuration-copious pus discharge that is thin, slimy, blackish and looks like a frost
4) Snayu	Greasy, thick; similar to mucoid nasal discharge and mixed with blood
5) Asthi	Like water shell of an oyster, mixed with marrow and with greasy blood discharge
6) Sandhi	No discharge on applying pressure; discharge on sudden movements; sticky, slimy and appears as if churned with blood.
7)Koshtha	Secretion mixed with blood, urine, faecal matter, pus and water
8) Marma	Depending upon involvement of organs

C. Prognosis of Vrana

According to prognosis, Sushruta divided Vrana into two primary categories: Kritya, which is curable, and Akritya, which is not (Incurable). The Sushruta Samhita provides a description of the prognosis based on the patient's age, strength, the location and nature of the vata, any related diseases, the type of discharge, and the smell of the vata.

Patients with a strong body, good age, good control over their habits, and good physical health can be cured. Due to the body's innate ability to renew tissues more quickly, Vrana recovers more quickly in youth. When a patient has a decent physical appearance and firm, well-developed muscles, there is less chance that using sharp objects may harm vital tissues like ligaments and veins. Due to eating habits that are regulated, powerful patients do not get fatigue even after experiencing pain. Patients who are in charge of their behaviors do not have any issues following surgical treatments.

Yapya is the term used to describe a type of wound where the patient could die right away if treatment is stopped. In addition to the categories already stated, Asadhya Vrana are Vrana that are incurable. Such is a brain injury that releases fluid similar to cerebrospinal fluid. Agantuja Varana's discharge, which includes fatty tissues, bone marrow, and CSF, is irreversible. It is incurable for abdominal injuries to cause urine and feces to discharge through the Vrana. Individuals who are malnourished and have Vrana, characterized by abundant pus discharged with blood and comorbidities such as dyspepsia and respiratory tract infections, exhibit a really terrible reaction to the medication, meaning their prognosis is poor. Vrana with discharge and odor not listed in doshic categories have a poor prognosis. Patients who live in a residence shielded from environmental pollution, particularly air pollution, follow their surgeon's instructions, and don't sleep during the day heal faster from vana.

D. Concept of wound healing in Ayurveda

The Sanskrit term for healing is ropana. Literally, "vranaropana" refers to the healing of the vrana (wound as well as ulcer). As an alternative, Charaka states that Vrana with a floor that is not very

red, pale, or brownish black, nor connected to extreme pain, hypergranulation, or pus pockets are good candidates for Vrana healing. The healing of Vrana involves four processes, viz.

- 1) Dushta awastha (inflammation stage)
- 2) The granulation tissue stage, or Shuddha awastha.
- 3) Ruhyamana awastha, or the remodeling and maturation stage
- 4) Rudha awastha, or contraction stage

There are four phases in NijaVrana's healing process. Shuddha awastha is the first stage in AgantujaVrana, and the remaining four stages correspond to the healing of NijaVrana.

1) DushtaVrana : The exact meaning of the term Dushta is "bad, wicked, offensive, and culpable." DushtaVrana is characterized as a type of Vrana wherein the vitiation of all four doshas results in a chronic form of Vrana that manifests as symptoms such as profuse exudates, bad odor, inflammation, etc. Stated otherwise, DushtaVrana is a Vrana that does not exhibit the characteristics of ShuddhaVrana, or a clean wound.

2) ShuddhaVrana : Shuddha Vrana is defined as having no pain or discharge, blackish-white borders from pure blood flow, granulation tissue at the surface level, and none of the three vitiated doshas or any consequences.

3) RuhyamanaVrana : Ruhyamana Vrana are those that have a pigeon-colored (grey) border, no exudates, and a partial layer of skin epithelium (shveta known as charmacheli or chipitika).

4) RudhaVrana : RudhaVrana is the Vrana whose floor has fully healed, has the same color and skin tone, and is neither indurated, bloated, or uncomfortable.

E. Factors affecting VranaRopana

1. Age: Because of their young metabolic rates and accelerated rate of body cell regeneration, Vrana patients heal more quickly than elderly patients.

2. Addiction: According to Sushruta, individuals who are in control of their addictions, such as drunkenness, are the best candidates for Vrana therapy.

3. Site: Vrana on the cheek, forehead, buttocks, and genitalia heals more quickly and with fewer complications. On the other hand, Vrana on the axilla, umbilicus, mouth, eyes, and perineal raphe is challenging to cure.

4. Bandaging: Inadequate bandaging retards the healing process of Vrana.

5. Maggots: In Vrana, maggots postpone healing.

6. Foreign body: Charaka said that when Vrana has poison or a foreign body, healing is delayed.

7. Related illness: Vrana has a hard time healing from poisoning, diabetes, skin conditions, and TB.

8. Nutrition: According to Sushruta, people with DushtaVrana who are malnourished would not recover. He added that treating people with food restrictions is simple.

9. Diet: Vrana quickly restores health to those who consume boiling rice from an ancient crop, bland vegetables, a limited amount of semisolid food, wild animal meat, radish, pomegranate, and Indian gooseberry fruit. According to Charaka, eating too much, consuming foods that contradict each other, and consuming unhealthful food can all cause Vrana's mending to take

longer. Sleep: It is simple to treat patients who consistently sleep at night and wake up during the day.

10. Emotions: Prolonged sadness and rage hinder the healing process.

11. Sex: Having sex while a wound is healing can cause it to heal more slowly. According to Sushruta, having sex while undergoing vrana healing can potentially be fatal.

12. Place of patient: Patients who are housed in Vranitagara (a ward that is well-located, shielded from the sun and drafts, and maintained tidy and clean) have a better chance of recovering.

F. Treatment of Vrana

Even though wound care has come a long way in recent years, managing vagina has always been a serious health concern, dating back to the time of Sushruta. Many operations are carried out for different stages of Vrana's recovery. Of these, Dushta Vrana is treated based on the participation of vitiated doshas, Vrana's location, severe putrefication and alterations in inflammation, whereas Shuddha Vrana is treated using ropana medicines. Sushruta explains wounds in relation to the treatment of numerous illnesses, such as abscesses and inflammatory oedema. In general, sixty distinct methods of managing Vrana were mentioned by Sushruta. Sushruta divides management into two basic categories: management of vrana (wound) and management of vrani (wounded). Of the sixty methods listed in Table 7, forty are related to transforming Dushta Vrana into Shuddha Vrana and are listed in the top four categories. These include surgical procedures, managing inflammation, treating non-healing wounds, and managing vitiated doshas. The notion of wound bed preparation, which was thoroughly explained by Susruta thousands of years ago, is still very much in use today.

T A B L E 7 Sixty procedures for Vrana's administration

Types	Number	Name
1. Control of vitiated doshas	10	1) nasal medication 2) use of errhines 3) gargling 4) smoking with medicinal drugs 5) enema 6) douching 7) purgation 8) emesis 9) bloodletting 10) internal oleation
2. Control of inflammation	8	1) food abstinence 2) application of local paste 3) irrigation 4) Anointing 5) fomentation 6) gentle massage 7) application of poultice 8) methods to induce suppuration
3. Surgical measures	13	1) excision 2) incision 3) bursting by medication 4) scraping 5) probing 6) extraction 7) puncturing 8) drainage 9) suturing 10) wound edge approximation 11) squeezing out by application of drug 12) haemostasis 13) instrumentation
4. For non healing wounds	9	1) covering with leaves 2) depilation 3) cauterisation 4) application of caustics 5) hardening 6) softening 7) removal of over granulation 8) encouraging granulation tissue formation 9) warming application Instead of these, seven cleansing procedures by use of decoctions, wicks, pastes, medicated butter milk and oil, thickened

		extract, dusting powder also comes under this category
5. For clean wound	9	1) bandaging 2) application of honey and butter milk 3) seven healing procedures by use of decoctions, wicks, pastes, medicated butter milk and oil, thickened extract, dusting powder Suturing and edge approximation mentioned in surgical measures.
6. For pain management	2	1) fumigation of Vrana 2) cooling application
7. Restoring normalcy of scar	4	1) pigmenting procedure 2) depigmenting procedure 3) restoration normal skin colour 4) encouraging hair growth
8. Dietary regimen	2	1) restorative measures 2) light, warm, demulcent, appetizing diet
9. Protective	1	1) protecting from invisible creatures
10. Miscellaneous	2	1) removal of maggots 2) neutralizing poison

G. Complications of Vrana

Two categories can be used to group Vrana complications:

1. Local complications: distinct varieties of doshic Vrana explain distinct sorts of smell, discharge, pain, color, shape, size, margins, and edge.

2. Systemic complications: fever, vomiting, loss of taste, indigestion, dyspnea, coughing, hiccups, diarrhoea, and increased thirst. Depending on the participation of doshas and the location of the lesion, secondary diseases such as erysipelas, hemiplegia (in the event of a head injury), convulsions, coma, schizophrenia (in the event of a head injury, animal bite such as a dog), and jaw lock can also result from a significant wound.

Conclusion

The radiance and beauty found in old Ayurvedic literature are so amply reflected in the following thorough description. Each and every facet of a wound (Vrana) has been thoroughly explored and explained by the Acharyas. This description makes it abundantly evident that they have a thorough understanding of the illness and are therefore qualified to treat it. Furthermore, if we contrast this description with that of contemporary medicine, we see that the latter's understanding of wounds is identical to that of old Ayurvedic books written thousands of years ago. Thus, it is imperative to comprehend the Ayurvedic notions of wound and its care in the modern era, as they greatly aid in a deeper comprehension of this illness and its appropriate treatment as well..

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